

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B276
 Date: 05 March 2007
 Take Off: 11:20:00Z
 Landing: 17:06:46Z
 Flight Time: 5h46m46

Campaign: GFDEX – Barrier Wind / Surface Fluxes

Operating Area: Denmark Strait

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Ian Renfrew	University of East Anglia
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	AVAPS / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Kent Moore	University of Toronto
9	Mission Scientist 3	Tom Haine	John Hopkins
10	Mission Scientist 4	Dave Sproson	UEA
11	Mission Scientist 5	Shunli Zhang	University of Toronto
12	Mission Scientist 6	Erik Kolstad	University of Bergen
13			
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B276
 Date: 5/3/07
 Project: GFDEX - Barrier Winds
 Location: Denmark Strait

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
112639	123539	Run 1	3.2 - 0.93 kft	280	
113033		T/O	2.2 kft	280	around 11:20:00
113328		qnh	1.5 kft	246	972mb
120903		qnh	1.6 kft	310	975mb
121845		qnh	1.5 kft	311	977 mb
123302		QNH	1.0 kft	308	983 mb
123539	131334	Run 2	0.93 - 0.68 kft	306	
131334	134001	Run 3			
125035		qnh	0.80 kft	328	988mb
130453		qnh	0.71 kft	331	991 mb
134001	135935	Run 4	0.70 - 0.81 kft	134	
135801		qnh	0.81 kft	132	989mb
140101	140947	Run 5	0.79 - 0.78 kft	340	
141104	144222	Run 6	0.73 - 0.82 kft	051	
144349	145659	Run 7	0.83 - 0.94 kft	153	
144800		qnh	0.89 kft	123	986
145851	153142	Run 8	2.8 kft	344	
153202	154516	Profile 1	2.8 - 21.0 kft	313	
153905		Profile 1	14.0 kft	300	interrupt
154049		Profile 1	14.0 kft	127	resume
154533	160916	Run 9	21.0 kft	128	
154631		Sonde 1	21.0 kft	127	
155008		Sonde 2	21.0 kft	141	
155315		Sonde 3	21.0 kft	141	
155625		Sonde 4	21.0 kft	140	
155941		Sonde 5	21.0 kft	140	
160252		Sonde 6	21.0 kft	140	
160609		Sonde 7	21.0 kft	140	
160916		Sonde 8	21.0 kft	140	
161133	165251	Run 10	21.0 - 20.3 kft	077	
170646		Land	1.5 kft	087	at Keflavik

B276 Track 05-MAR-07

GFDex Sortie Brief – B276 – 5 March 2007
Barrier Wind and Surface Fluxes (Plan 22)

Mission Scientists: Ian Renfrew, Kent Moore, Tom Haine, Dave Sproson,

Aims

- Investigate the structure of barrier winds along the Southeast Coast of Greenland
- Map out the heat fluxes associated with the barrier winds
- Total dropsondes 7; Total distance ~1200 nm; Total time ~5 h.

GFD22	Time	Manoeuvre	Distance (nm)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	1030	Take off Keflavík , transit to 64°25N, 31°30W	235	~60	~60
2		Straight low-level run at 100 ft (or MSA) across the barrier wind and temperature gradient Heading ~320 deg to 65°45N 33°55W	109	33	~93
3		Straight low-level run at 100 ft (or MSA) over the sea ice zone to 64°50N, 36°50W.	92	28	~121
4		Straight low-level run at 100 ft (or MSA) across the barrier wind and temperature gradient Heading ~140 deg 63°30N, 34°30W.	100	30	~151
5		Turn and repeat leg heading 320 deg to MID SW	50	15	~166
6		Straight low-level run at 100 ft (or MSA) into the barrier wind heading ~50 deg to MID NE	94	28	~194
7		Turn to heading 140 deg, low-level 100 ft leg to 64°25N, 31°30W	59	18	~212
8		Turn to heading ~320 deg, climb to 2000 ft, straight level leg to 65°45N 33°55W	109	33	~245
9		Profile ascent about 2000 ft per minute			
10		High-level dropsonde leg, heading 140 deg, from 65°45N 33°55W to 64°25N, 31°30W. 7 Dropsonde releases (every 14 nm), not including the start point.	109	20	~265
11		Return to Keflavik	234	~40	~305

Mission Scientists Debriefing Sheet

Flight No. **B276 – Barrier Wind and Surface Fluxes (Plan 22)**

Date: **5 March 2007**

Aims

- Investigate the structure of barrier winds along the Southeast Coast of Greenland
- Map out the heat fluxes associated with the barrier winds
- Total dropsondes 7; Total distance ~1200 nm; Total time ~5 h.

Assessment of the Flight

Highly successful.

Take off was delayed by 50 minutes due to INU and Horace problems.

After problems with the turbulence probe freezing up in the previous barrier winds flight (B274), this time a low-level transit and then doing the low-level legs first tack was used. This worked well. The turbulence probe worked for all the low-level legs, but was “lost” on the ascent at around 2000 feet. This did make the flight somewhat arduous with 3.5 hours at 100ft. First low-level leg was (tactically) extended to reach 100% sea ice cover – this worked well. Stunning views of sea ice and Greenland.

Second cross-wind low-level leg was cut a little short, due to fuel use before take off.

Low-level leg into wind worked well. 2000 ft leg should give barrier wind structure, Stratocumulus deck cloud tops are around 2000 ft. Ascent over sea ice and high-level dropsonde leg with 8 sondes – all worked well.

Summary of weather conditions

Synoptic-scale low pressure south of Iceland, so large-scale easterly flow, influenced by Greenland to give homogeneous barrier flow. Low and mid-level cloud. Clearer towards Greenland and over sea ice zone.

Ian Renfrew

side slip ~

static = ~ 70 mb
 attitude diff = ~ 8
 side slip diff = 0
 attitude check = 100
 side slip = 1213

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.376** Date **5 March** Name **Ian Renfrew** Page of

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:20	1				Take off
11:26	1	2000			2000 ft.
11:30	1	1000			Lots of tactical physics to avoid cloud & precipitation.
11:51	1	200			Heiman calibration.
11:55	1	4500			—
12:02	1	3200			low cloud base low
12:06	1	500 ft			
12:20	1	1000 ft			At 1000 ft for 1-2 min
12:35		100 ft			Calibration of Heiman.
12:38	2	"			North run for calibration
12:38	2	"		64° 25' 31.30"	Turn onto Run 2
12:51	2	"			Cloud edge at low levels
12:54	2	"			lanes Mid NE
13:06	2	"			First sea ice lumps
"	2	"			SST gradient
13:07	2	"			1/10ths sea ice
13:09	2				2/10ths
13:10	2				exp. to lumps
13:11	2				8/10ths
13:12	2				6/10ths
13:13	2				9/10ths End of Run
13:14	3				Beautiful views over sea ice ~ 9/10ths
13:29	3				Polygon 5/10ths

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.276** Date **5 March** Name **Ian Renfer** Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:30	3	100			Much more open water
13:34	3	100			Heiman Calibration.
13:39	4	100			Turn into next run
13:40	4	100			Start of Run
13:50	4	100			Power on laptop gone
13:55	4	100			Shot Laptop.
~14:00	4	100-200			End of Run
14:01	5	100			Start of Run
14:10	5	100			End of Run
14:11	6	100			Start of Run mid SW to mid NE
14:19	6	100			327 / 15 knots.
14:43	6	100			End of Run
14:44	7	200			Turn
14:44	7	100			Start of Run to 64°25N 31°30W
14:49	7	100			Coming into cloud, but below cloud deck.
14:56	7	100			End of Run
	8	100			Climb & turn.
14:59	8	2000			Start of Run. (Concern about idios)
15:05	8	2000			Loosing turbulence probe.
15:10	8	2000			At top of STC deck.
15:10	8	"			Ozone dropped?
15:31	8	"			End of leg.
15:37	9				Climb. - 2000 ft per min. (Isothermal to ~2000 ft)
15:45	9	"			End of ascent.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B276

Date: 05/03/07

Operator: KFT

Page 1 of 1

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:20				U/S							Heaters on just after T/O
11:30:00	143	0.06	1	-	1.5	800	3	33	3200	3	1 st 2D pictures 2000FT
11:32:30	130	0.07	2	-	4.5	650	1	641	1600	1	300FT
11:34:00											Heaters off (+3.5C)
11:35:00	95	0.14	6	-	11	650	1	625	1600	1	
11:40:00	112	0.09	9	-	5.5	800	1	383	1200	1	FFSSP bases increased
11:45:00	140	0.08	12	-	1	800	1	125	1200	1	
11:50:00	123	0.09	18	-	1.5	800	1	750	1200	1	
11:55:00	184	0.08	23	-	3.5	600	1	250	2400	1	500FT
12:00:00	125	0.10	30	-	8	775	1	1800	1200	1	
12:05:00	137	0.15	41	-	7	600	1	958	1200	1	300FT
12:10:00	120	0.08	44	-	3.5	700	1	358	800	1	500FT
12:22:00	120	0.14	50	-	12.5	700	1	75	800	1	
12:28:00	250	0.09	64	-	55	500	2,5,1	2700	1200	2,1	200FT
12:30:00	267	0.10	68	-	11	525	1	733	800	2	
12:35:00	234	0.08	71	-	2	300	1	50	800	1	100FT – Heaters ON
12:40:00	221	0.07	73	-	2.5	300	1,8	0	0		FFSSP signal base increased
12:45:00	174	0.07	74	-	2.5	200	8,11	0	0		
12:50:00	226	0.07	76	-	0.5	200	1,8	0	0		
12:55:00	215	0.07	77	-	0	0		0	0		
13:00:00	130	0.06	77	-	0	0		0	0		
13:05:00	140	0.06	77	-	0	0		0	0		
13:10:00	109	0.07	78	-	0	0		0	0		
13:15:00	131	0.06	78	-	0	0		0	0		
13:20:00	259	0.06	78	-	0	0		0	0		
13:25:00	214	0.07	78	-	0	0		0	0		
13:30:00	101	0.07	78	-	0	0		0	0		
13:35:00	212	0.06	78	-	0	0		0	0		
13:40:00	159	0.07	79	-	0	0		0	0		
13:45:00	123	0.07	79	-	0	0		0	0		
13:55:00	170	0.08	81	-	0	0		0	0		
14:00:00	192	0.07	83	-	0	0		0	0		End of Run
14:10:00	151	0.07	87	-	0	0		0	0		
14:15:00	194	0.08	88	-	0	0		0	0		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B276

Date: 05/03/07

Operator: KFT

Page 2 of 2

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:20:00	173	0.07	90	-	0	0		0	0		Some 2DC images of NaCl
14:25:00	155	0.07	91	-	0	0		0	0		
14:30:00	177	0.07	93	-	0	0		0	0		
14:35:00	239	0.07	94	-	0	0		0	0		
14:40:00	172	0.06	95	-	0	0		0	0		
14:42:21	151	0.07	96	-	5	100	8	0	0		NaCl on 2DC? End run 6
14:43:48	160	0.06	96	-	0	0		0	0		Start run 7
14:50:00	164	0.07	99	-	2	100	8	0	0		
14:54:00	240	0.07	102	-	15	200	1 (<0C)	366	200	1	
14:57:00	307	0.11	105	-	32	325	1 (<0C)	491	325	1	End run, start profile
14:58:50	594	0.20	312	-	73.5	350	1 (<0C)	1258	350	1	Start run 8
15:00:00	331	0.19	521	-	113	350	1,11	58	250	1	T=MS05
15:02:00	366	0.20	742	-	102	375	1	125	375	1	T=MS06
15:04:00	333	0.18	972	-	139	250	11	175	250		Ffssp locked up
15:06:00	541	0.14	55	-	228	500	11	491			FFSSP restarted
15:08:00	394	0.08	213	-	300	375	11	NOISE?			
15:10:00	131	0.06	237	-	NOISE			NOISE			
15:12:00	219	0.06	237	-	NOISE			NOISE			
15:15:00	203	0.06	237	-	NOISE			NOISE			
15:31:25	119	0.06	237	-	NOISE			NOISE			END RUN 8
15:43			Bases increas'd					Data rate 1Hz			
15:46:33	91	0.06	238	-	NOISE			NOISE			SONDE 1
15:50:09	71	0.06	238	-	NOISE			NOISE			SONDE 2
15:50:50	54	0.09	238	-	265	400	8,11	NOISE			
15:53:16	129	0.09	242	-	198	725	8,11	NOISE			SONDE 3
15:56:26	119	0.06	245	-	115	225	8,11	NOISE			SONDE 4
15:58											FFSSP BASES INCR
15:59:41	80	0.06	300	-	72	275	8,11	NOISE			SONDE 5 – FFSSP V'S awry
16:02:52	69	0.10	1	-	189	575	4,9,11	NOISE			SONDE 6
16:06:07	75	0.06	7	-	116	550	8,9,11	NOISE			SONDE 7
16:09:16	89	0.07	16	-	162	375	8,11	NOISE			SONDE 8, END RUN 9
16:28											CIP RESTARTED (froze 1600)
16:30:00	95	0.16	33	-	199	400	8	NOISE			
16:35:43	107	0.07	44	-	129	500	9,11,8	NOISE			

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B276 **T/O:** 113033
Date of flight: 05/03/07 **Land:** 170646

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B276
Date of Flight: 05/03/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	35862 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 348909
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 67022 Blocks written = 67022 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 113000 End = 170700 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Noise on 2DP from 15:05 onwards. Some noise on 2DC from 16:14 Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 113000 End = 170700 101pp 2DC 115pp 2DP FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = A</p> <p>Start = 113000 End = 170700</p> <p>Time data processed to = 170644 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 11021, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = A Y = (X+1) = B</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	Y	<p>Correlated? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B276
Date of Flight: 05/03/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.15 113000 170700
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = B Y = X+1 = C
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	Y	Merged OK? Y

Flight:

B276

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

**Report Created 15/03/2007
12:14:14**

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

14/03/2007 15:55:42

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B276

Date: 05 March 2007

Instruments

1.

Aircraft

1.

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

ISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B276:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	26 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Rearward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dr Ian A. Renfrew

Dr Ian A. Renfrew
Reader in Climate System Dynamics
School of Environmental Sciences
University of East Anglia
Norwich, NR4 7TJ, United Kingdom
Room: 2.33

Tel: +44 (0) 1603 592557
Fax: +44 (0) 1603 591327

E-mail: i.renfrew@uea.ac.uk

Daily weather summary 5 March 2007

<p>Large scale situation today:</p>	<p>A 954 hPa elongated low pressure system is located ~200 km south of eastern Iceland and a 966 low about 500km west of Ireland. Just north-northeast of Newfoundland there is a 984 hPa cyclone.</p>
<p>Features of interest:</p>	<p>The cyclone to the south of Iceland is resulting in strong winds over the northwestern peninsula as well as over Denmark Strait. The forecast for 12Z (+12h) is NE-ly 30-40kt, but calmer close to Greenland in lee of Cape Tobin. By midnight the prediction is for more northerly winds, up to 50kt north of the northwestern peninsula. Large latent and sensible heat fluxes are expected off the sea ice.</p> <p>HIRLAM-T: Sensible (colored) and latent (contours) heat flux at the surface. IT: Mon. 05. Mar. 2007 00Z VT: Mon. 05.03.2007 12Z (+12 h)</p>
<p>Action:</p>	<p>A Denmark Strait south barrier flow flight is planned.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 24-48 hours:</p>	<p>The main cyclone south of Iceland is quasi-stationary while the cyclone west of Ireland moves to the north-northeast and in the end merges into the main cyclone. In the UK global 48h forecast the centre pressure is 959hPa. There are still strong winds over Denmark Strait, at 12Z (36h forecast) the 925 hPa winds are northeasterly to north-northeasterly 50-70kt in Denmark Strait north. The cyclone by Newfoundland moves slowly northward.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 48-96 hours:</p>	<p>The cyclone of Iceland dissipates while the Newfoundland low moves eastward and seems to split up in two parts, with one part moving north-northeastward while the other part moves more eastward and dissipating. There are still strong winds over Denmark Strait and western Irminger Sea but little signs of W-ly tip jets.</p>